

EFFECT OF BOARD CHARACTERISTICS ON CARBON EMISSION: EVIDENCE FROM OIL AND GAS FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study ascertained the effect of board characteristics on carbon emission disclosure of oil and gas firms in Nigeria from 2012-2024, using board size, and audit committee size as the independent variables. Data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the nine oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Ex-Post Facto research design was employed for the study. The study employed Pearson correlation coefficient and Panel least square regression analysis to test the hypotheses. Conclusively, the results of the tested hypotheses revealed that board size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure and audit committee size has a significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure. The study suggested amongst others that large number of board of directors should be encouraged; hence, the large board's size positively influences carbon emission disclosure and firm performance through effective monitoring and supervisory*

Keywords: *Board size, and Audit committee and Carbon emission disclosure*

Introduction

In recent times, corporate governance has attracted interest among scholars. Due to the collapse of multinational companies that were regarded as too big to fail such as Enron, Dot-Com, Bubble, Tyco, Xerox, Ocean Bank, Parmalat, Cadbury and so on. This led to loss of investors confidence in the capital market especially the oil and gas industry. In order to restore stakeholders' confidence, there was need to introduce a code of corporate governance that would regulate the activities of the board of directors that have become so powerful. In the USA, the Sarbanes-Oxley Act was enacted in 2002 also known as the "Public Company Accounting Reform and Investor Protection Act" which regulates the public company boards, management and public accounting firms. In Nigeria, there were sectorial corporate governance code such as code of Corporate Governance for the Telecommunication

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Industry 2016, code of Corporate Governance for Banks and Discount Houses in Nigeria 2014, code of Corporate Governance for Public Companies in Nigeria 2011, code of Good Corporate Governance for Insurance Industry in Nigeria 2009 and Code of Corporate for Licensed Fund Operators 2008. In 2018, the Nigeria Code of Corporate Governance was introduced to institutionalize corporate governance best practices in Nigeria companies as a key driver to corporate accountability and business prosperity (Ubeh, Okoye, Nwoye & Amahalu, 2024) Bunyaminua, Yakubu and Oumarou (2025) documented that corporate governance is the set of processes, customs, policies, laws and regulations affecting the way a corporation or company is controlled. It is the system by which organizations are directed and control (Riyadha, Al-shmamb and Mohammed, 2024). It focuses on the associations among management, board of directors, controlling shareholders, minority shareholders and other stakeholders (Osundina, Olayinka & Chukwuma, 2016). The board is imperative for the company's governance, and it is essential to have conclusive and result-oriented board activities in the companies. Corporate governance has drawn the attention of investors and government after the incidence of the 2007 financial crisis worldwide. The Cadbury Report issued by The Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance in 1992, titled - Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance, which has given recommendations for corporate boards, describes it as a mechanism by which companies are governed. The onus is on the board to ensure the implementation of strategies according to the framed policies, reduce the agency problem and enhance firm value in the best interests of shareholders. Boards of directors have been largely criticized for the decline in shareholders' wealth and corporate failure. They have been in the spotlight for the fraud cases that had resulted in the failure of major corporations, such as Enron, Enron, WorldCom, Marconi, Parmalat, Cadbury and Global Crossing. In Nigeria, a series of widelyl-publicized cases of accounting improprieties have been recorded (for example, Savannah Bank Plc, Society Generale Bank Ltd, Oceanic Bank, Bank of the North, AfriBank, Mainstream Bank, Wema Bank, Oceanic Bank, NAMPAK, Finbank, Spring Bank etc). Climate change is one of the biggest environmental challenges society faces in the 21st century. As companies and their industrial production processes have a huge stake in the overall level of global GHG emissions, curbing these emissions can be seen as a central part of a firm's corporate responsibility agenda. Carbon dioxide gas can be toxic and very harmful to humans, it increases the temperature of the Earth's atmosphere, it causes the global warming effect that has bad effects on the Earth. One of the most significant barriers to widespread deployment of carbon management technologies is high cost, transportation challenges, storage considerations, uncertain public support, lack of capacity within the organisation, including inadequate funds for adaptation, and an organisational culture that limits or prevents decision-making on adaptation.

The decision dilemma facing corporate managers is that they cannot only focus on value creation ignoring the impact of its operation on the atmosphere. On the other hand, managers' financial

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obligations restrict them to take projects that can only meet social obligations without reasonable economic outcome. Growing scientific evidence shows that carbon management is a serious challenge and uncontrolled global warming will cause enormous damage. Therefore, given the importance of any board, it is vital to identify and assess their characteristics such as board size, board gender, board independence, audit committee size and its consequent effect on carbon emission disclosure.

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of board characteristics on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of board size on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria
- ii. Evaluate the effect of audit committee size on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Board Characteristics

Kanakriyah (2021) states that the board of directors is agents to the company, they are made up of persons who oversee the activities of a company. The primary purpose of the board is to monitor and advise the top management in the discharge of their responsibilities to the owners (Okolie & Uwejean, 2022). A board of directors is a group of people who jointly supervise the activities of an organization, which can be either a for-profit business, nonprofit organization, or a government agency. Such a board's powers, duties, and responsibilities are determined by government regulations (including the jurisdiction's corporation's law) and the organization's own constitution and bylaws. These authorities may specify the number of members of the board, how they are to be chosen, and how often they are to meet. As the size of the board increases, interpersonal communication becomes less effective. As the board size increases, problems of communication and coordination manifest and are likely to develop factions and conflict (Mofijul & Maksudur, 2019).

Aurelian, Dumitrescu, Micu and Lobda (2022), reported that good board characteristics practice reduces borrowing costs, adds values to firm, and improves risk management, which eventually lead to sustainable growth and improved firm's performance. Aigbovorhiuwa, Adediran and Achimugu (2022) stated that the board of director plays a crucial role in corporate governance especially with regard to board characteristics such as; composition, size, diversity, committee structure, the frequency of meetings, styles, structure, processes, activities and their relationship. The aim of good board characteristics often is to prevent irregularities, scandals, and ensure the smooth governance of corporations (Githaiga, Kabete & Bonareri, 2022).

Board Size

Board size refers to the total number of directors on the board of each sample firm which is inclusive of the CEO and Chairman for each accounting year. This will include outside directors, executive directors and non-executive directors (Segal, 2021). Board size is the number of directors that make up the board (Gordon, 2021). An optimal board size should include both the executive and non-executive directors (Fariha, Hossain & Ghosh, 2022). The effectiveness in structuring the board is important for governing the company. Board size has been found to vary between one country and another as every country has different cultures. This means that there has no optimal and standard board size among the companies in the world (Rajeevan & Ajward, 2020). According to a study by The Wall Street Journal, the smallest board size has an average of 9.5 board directors. Large boards are defined as those with 14 or more board directors. Overall, companies have an average of 11.2 board directors (Adebayo, Ringim & Shaib, 2022). Bylaws can set the number of board members, how the board is elected (for example, by a shareholder vote at an annual meeting), and how often the board meets. While there is no set number of members for a corporate board, many pursuing diversity as well as cohesion settles on a range of 8 to 12 directors (Musa, Adamu, & Hussaini, 2024).

Audit Committee Size

In order to perform their role effectively, audit committees should have adequate resources and authority to discharge their increasing responsibilities. Altin (2024) argues that the larger the audit committee, the more likely it is to uncover and resolve potential problems in the financial reporting process, because it is likely to provide the necessary strength and diversity of views and expertise to ensure effective monitoring. This suggests that audit committee size is an integral factor for firms in delivering meaningful corporate reporting. However, it can also be argued that as the number of audit committee members increases, each may be comforted by the presence of others and free riders emerge (Shahsavari, Salehi & Bagherpour-Valashani, 2023). In addition, larger audit committees are also likely to suffer from process losses and diffusion of responsibility (An, 2023). The Smith Report (2003) recommends a minimum of three non-executive directors. According to SEC Code of Corporate Governance 2011, the audit committee should consist of not less than three directors of which independent directors should have the majority, and the committee is chaired by independent nonexecutive director.

Carbon Emissions Disclosure

Emission is the production and discharge of something, especially gas or radiation (Ika, et al, 2022). Hermawan, et al (2018) stated that emission is anything that is been released out into the open. But more often it refers to gases being released into the air, like greenhouse gasses or emissions from power plants and factories. Emissions are basically chemicals in exhaust gases that are harmful to air quality, mainly carbon monoxide (CO), hydrocarbons (HC), and nitrogen oxides (NO). Carbon emission is the release of carbon into the atmosphere (Budiharta & Kacaribu, 2020). Emission is an

amount of something, especially a gas that harms the environment that is sent out into the air (Attenborough, 2022). A carbon price is a cost applied to carbon pollution to encourage polluters to reduce the amount of greenhouse gas they emit into the atmosphere (Liu & Kong, 2021). A carbon price is the method widely agreed to be the most efficient way for nations to reduce global warming emissions. To Habib and Hasan (2020), it is a cost applied to carbon pollution to encourage polluters to reduce the amount of greenhouse gases they emit into the atmosphere: it usually takes the form either of a carbon tax or a requirement to purchase permits to emit, generally known as carbon emissions trading.

Empirical Review

Ogbulafor, Alpheaus and Azubuike (2025) investigated the effect of board characteristics on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria, focusing on CEO duality and audit committee size from 2013 to 2022. Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and panel data techniques based on robust least squares regression, were used to analyze the data. The methodology accounted for non-normality and heteroscedasticity in the dataset, using Huber regression and M-estimation procedures to reduce the influence of outliers. The study indicated that CEO duality and audit committee size showed no significant effect on ROA. Dinh Dang and Trinh (2025) studied the significance of corporate governance (CG) in the banking sector, specifically in the context of Industry form 2014 to 2023. The study employed the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach. The results indicate that the presence of both gender diversity and nationality diversity have a favorable effect on the performance of banks. Louziri and Oubal (2025) ascertained the effect of chairman characteristics on dividend policy within Moroccan firms listed on the Casablanca Stock Exchange, from 2003 to 2018). A fixed effects panel data model was employed, incorporating six control variables—firm age, growth opportunities, size, board size, female representation, and foreign ownership. The results demonstrated that chairman age and tenure significantly affect dividend policy. Older chairmen are more risk-averse, favoring higher dividend distributions to ensure financial stability, while longer-tenured chairmen tend to retain earnings for aggressive investments, reflecting overconfidence. Che, Hope and Langli (2020) examined the effect of board composition on the financial performance of FTSE100 United Kingdom (UK) using Panel least square regression models between 2010 and 2011 periods. The study found that board independence and the proportion of foreign directors in the total number of directors (as characteristics of corporate board composition) have a significant positive impact on return on assets of firms. Okon (2020) determined the relationship between board characteristics and company performance (measured by turnover) in Nigeria from 2010 to 2012. The study used multiple regression technique on 90 sampled firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study showed that board size and financial expertise are positively and significantly related to turnover. EL-Maude, Jibreel, Bawa, Ahmed and Shamaki (2020) studied the effect of board size,

board composition and board meetings on the financial performance of listed consumer goods in Nigeria over the period of ten years from 2006 to 2015. The study used ex-post facto research design and purposive sampling technique as research design and sampling technique. The data were analyzed by means of descriptive statistics, Correlation and Regression analysis using STATA (version 11). The regression result concluded that smaller board size are more effective than larger board size, good proportion of board composition is a good factor to enhance ROA. Oyedokun (2019) examined the effect of board characteristics on financial performance of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria for the period 2013-2017. Ex-post Facto research design was adopted. The linear regression result showed that board characteristics have a significant effect on Tobin's Q of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria Oyerogba, Memba and Riro (2016) analyzed the effect of board size on the profitability of the listed firm from 2004 to 2013. Both descriptive and inferential statistics using correlation and panel least square (PLS) regression techniques were carried out. The study found that a significant positive relationship exists between the board size, firm size and return on capital employed. Fuzi, AbdulHalim and Julizaerma (2016) ascertained the association between board independence and firm performance in Pakistan firms using ANOVA. The study found a non-significant positive relationship between the proportion of independent directors and return on investment of sampled firms. Odudu, James and James (2016) determined the effect of board Characteristics on Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria from 2010-2015. Pooled OLS regression technique was applied to test the hypothesis of the study. The study revealed that the executive director has no significant influence on the return on equity of listed banks in Nigeria. Usman Shettima and Nazam Dzolkarnaini (2018) evaluated the relationship between board characteristics and microfinance banks performance in Nigeria from 2010 to 2013. The statistical instrument used was the fixed effect Panel least Square regression. The study revealed a negative and non-significant relation between female directors and return on assets of MFIs.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design will be employed in this study. This study was treated as ex-post facto research since it relied on historical data.

Population and Sample Size of the Study

The population of the study consists of the nine Oil and Gas firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group as at 31st December, 2024.

Source of Data

The data to be used in this study was collected mainly from secondary source. These data were obtained for thirteen (13) years annual reports and account and sustainability report from 2012-2024.

Method of Data Analysis

This study employed descriptive statistics which summarily describes the mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis, skewness, maximum and minimum values of the study variables. On the other hand, inferential data analysis will also be employed to test the hypotheses using statistical tools such as: Pearson Correlation Analysis and Panel least square (PLS) regression analysis via e-view 9.0. More so, the volume of carbon emission disclosure emission was measured by content analysis to find the degree of volume of carbon emission that was disclosed in Sustainability Reports.

Model Specification

This study adapted and modified the model of Okocha, Okoye, Amahalu, & Obi, (2022):

$$ERD = \beta_0 + \beta_1GDV_{it} + \beta_2BDSZ_{it} + \beta_3ACFE_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad \text{eq (i)}$$

Where :

ERD = Environmental Remediation Disclosure

BDSZ = Board Size

ACFE = Audit Committee Financial Expertise

Consequent upon the adapted model, the following regression equations were constructed:

Where:

β_0 = Constant term (intercept)

β_{it} = Coefficients of Board Characteristics for firm i in period t

μ_{it} = Error term/unexplained variable(s) of firm i in period t

CED_{it} = Carbon Emission Disclosure of firm i in period t

BDS_{it} = Board Size of firm i in period t

ACS_{it} =Audit Committee Size of firm i in period t

Decision Rule

Accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if the p-value of the test is greater than 0.05, otherwise reject and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1).

Data Analysis

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

	CED	BDS	ACS
Mean	0.3851	17.1506	0.0651
Median	0.7403	17.0000	0.0400
Maximum	1.2893	22.0000	0.0500
Minimum	0.6000	13.0000	0.0430
Std. Dev.	0.1856	1.7723	0.0058
Skewness	0.3567	1.5742	0.2970
Kurtosis	1.5772	5.5619	5.3451
Jarque-Bera	1.2373	7.972	6.7852

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Probability	0.5387	0.0051	0.0013
Sum	12.5620	221.0000	6.1700
Sum Sq.			
Dev.	0.4687	35.9986	0.1201

Observations 117 117 117

Source: E-Views 9.0 Descriptive Output, 2025

Table 1 depicts an average mean of 0.9054 for CED. This implies that on the average the sampled firms in Nigeria report about 90.54% of their environmental performance in their financial statements. The maximum value for carbon emission disclosure is 115%, minimum of 70% with a standard deviation of 0.1753. On the average, BDS stood at 16.1539. The implication is that on the average, the size of board members for the sampled firms is 16, with a standard deviation of 1.7723, a maximum number of directors of 21 and a minimum of 14. The maximum figure of ACS for the sample firms is 5 members on the audit committee while the minimum is 3 members with a standard deviation of 0.0058.

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho₂: Board size has no significant effect on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria

Table 2: Panel Least Square Regression Analysis testing the effect of BDS on CED

Dependent Variable: CED

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 11/06/25 Time: 20:21

Sample: 2012 2024

Periods included: 13

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 117

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.728190	0.147155	5.116179	0.0001
BDS	0.047125	0.009059	3.057716	0.0239

R-squared	0.224518	Mean dependent var	0.905385
Adjusted R-squared	0.216571	S.D. dependent var	0.169138
S.E. of regression	0.266858	Akaike info criterion	-0.726407
Sum squared resid	3.217815	Schwarz criterion	-0.679190

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Log likelihood	53.49479	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.707237
F-statistic	5.193139	Durbin-Watson stat	1.387102
Prob(F-statistic)	0.023654		

Source: E-Views 9.0 Regression Output, 2025

In table simple least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between board size (BDS) and carbon emission disclosure (CED). The R-squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings, the R squared was 0.22, showing that there was variation of 22% on CED due to changes in BDS. This implies that 22% changes in CED could be accounted for by BDS, while 78% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.387 suggests that the both model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 5.193 and the associated F-statistical probability is 0.024 showing statistical significant effect.

Decision:

The P-value of the test Prob(F-statistic) = 0.023654 is less than the α -value of 0.05; therefore H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. Since the p-value of the test is less than 0.05, the study uphold that board size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure of Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Audit committee size has no significant effect on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria

H₂: Audit committee size has significant effect on carbon emission disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria

Table 3: Panel Least Square Regression Analysis testing the effect of ACS on CED

Dependent Variable: CED

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 11/06/25 Time: 22:11

Sample: 2012 2024

Periods included: 13

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 117

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.599484	0.077207	7.764651	0.0000
ACS	0.644524	0.159697	4.035908	0.0021

R-squared	0.338921	Mean dependent var	0.176585
Adjusted R-squared	0.317824	S.D. dependent var	0.269138
S.E. of regression	0.158986	Akaike info criterion	-0.787609
Sum squared resid	2.976291	Schwarz criterion	-0.775842
Log likelihood	52.14896	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.803890
F-statistic	17.46728	Durbin-Watson stat	1.528911
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002598		

Source: E-Views 9.0 Regression Output, 2025

In table simple least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between audit committee size (ACS) and carbon emission disclosure (CED). The R-squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings, the R squared was 0.32, showing that there was variation of 32% on CED due to changes in ACS. This implies that 32% changes in CED could be accounted for by ACS, while 68% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.529 suggests that the both model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 17.467 and the associated F-statistic probability is 0.0026 showing statistical significant effect.

Decision:

The P-value of the test $\text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic}) = 0.002598$ is less than the α -value of 0.05; therefore H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected. Since the p-value of the test is less than 0.05, the study upholds that audit committee size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure of Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The regression result revealed that p-value of the test $\text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic})$ was 0.023654, less than the α -value of 0.05. The study upholds that board size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure of Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria. The result of this study is in line with the report of Adejola, Omonuk and Ojuola (2024); Pereira, Monteiro, Silva and Lima (2023) but disagreed with Ogbulafor, Alpheaus and Azubuike (2025); Nguyen, Pham, Truong, Phi, Le and Vu (2023).

The regression result showed that p-value of the test $\text{Prob}(F\text{-statistic})$ was 0.002598, less than the α -value of 0.05. The study upholds that audit committee size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure of Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria. This finding validates the findings of Kumar (2023); Louziri and Oubal (2025); but opposed the findings of Almustafa, Jabbouri and Kijkasiwat (2023).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study determined the effect of board characteristics on carbon emission disclosure of oil and gas firms listed in Nigeria from 2012-2024, using board size, and audit committee size while as the independent variables. The study extracted data from annual reports and account and publications of the sampled firms that operated during 2012-2024 with the aid of E-Views 9.0. Panel Least Square regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses. The study revealed that board size has significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure. Also audit committee size has a significant and positive effect on carbon emission disclosure. The study therefore, concludes that board characteristics have a significant and positive effect on Carbon emission disclosure of oil and gas firms listed in Nigeria.

On the premise of these study findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Large number of board of directors should be encouraged; hence, the large board's size positively influences carbon emission disclosure and firm performance through effective monitoring and supervisory.
- ii. Oil and gas firms in Nigeria should ensure firm compliance with the provisions of Companies and Allied Matters act of having equal representation of non-executive directors and independent directors to ensure effective oversight and resource readiness.

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